

DOI :

Geopolitics to Techno-Politics: Redefining power variables in International Relations in the Digital Age

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ABSTRACT

The contemporary world is experiencing a substantial overhaul of the established order of international relations. The power to influence global affairs is no longer defined by historical standards such as military superiority or by the Gross Domestic Product, but by the capabilities of high-end technologies. The on-going century can precisely be regarded as the age of Techno-polarity where the pursuit of technological dominance has become a strategic resource, wielding geopolitical power. As the lines between tech and geopolitics blur, the emerging powers like India would aspire to capture the future of emerging techno-polar world order that hinges on technological statecraft. This research article delves into the concept of techno-polarity, exploring how technological advancements are affecting variables of the global power equation. It explores the high-stakes interdependence of technology, power, and diplomacy in a world where the next technological advancement may shift the balance of power.

KEYWORDS: Geopolitics, power, techno-politics, digitalization and International Relations.

INTRODUCTION

Techno-polarity is the reconfiguration of global power where the control, development, and strategic deployment of advanced technologies shape the hierarchy of nations. It is defined by a nation's ability to innovate, regulate, and leverage digital and technological systems as critical assets in determining a state's power, international standing, and capacity to shape global governance.

The Bipolarity, during the Cold War period, was characterized by existence of power poles, the United States and the Soviet Union. These two blocs competed ideologically, militarily, and economically in shaping international relations, with expanding respective alliances, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) and the Warsaw Pact. In contrast, techno-

polarity does not feature a binary division of power but is characterized by a multipolar competition centred on technological dominance. Unlike the clear ideological

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Received	Reviewed	Accepted	Published
02-Feb.-2024	27-Mar.-2024	22-Apr.-2024	10-Jun.-2024

Volume	Issue	June	ISSN
No. 6	No. 1	2024	2583-1852(P), 2584-0878(O)

How to Cite this Article: Pradhan. R. K.; Bhatt. S; Shukla. S; Geopolitics to Techno-Politics: Redefining power variables in International Relations in the Digital Age. THE THIRD VOICE REALITY AND VISION. 2024. Vol No-6. Issue No1. June. Pp: 131-136. DOI:

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Quick Response Code: 	Available online at : thirdvoice.voiceforvoiceless.in
	DOI: Article No - TVRV00068

divide of the bipolar world, techno-polarity is driven by innovation in areas like artificial intelligence, 5G, and quantum computing, where multiple state and non-state actors compete without strict geopolitical alignments.

The collapse of the USSR, in a way, marked the triumph of Liberal ideology over the Communist trend of thought. Coming up of Bretton Woods institutions, which became the engines of ideological propagation, pulled the newly de-colonised nations on the table for cooperation talks, triggering a wave of Liberalisation-Privatisation-Globalization reforms in these erstwhile colonies. Despite a dreadful past, most of these colonies, including India, brought these reforms and entered a distinguished era of the unipolar world order marked by the United States' unparalleled dominance in global affairs. Techno-polarity diverges from unipolarity in that no single nation holds uncontested control over global technological and geopolitical landscapes. While the US remains a central player in the tech-driven world, rising powers such as China and the European Union challenge its dominance, creating a more decentralized and competitive environment.

The Global Financial Crisis of 2008 is considered the imperceptible yet consistent beginning of a shift towards a Multipolar world order. Multipolarity is characterized by the presence of several major powers—such as the United States, the European Union, Russia, and China—exercising influence across different regions and domains. Techno-polarity aligns with the concept of multipolarity, as power is dispersed across multiple actors. However, techno-polarity introduces new actors—private tech corporations—into the global power equation, altering the traditional state-centric nature by placing greater emphasis on control over emerging technologies and data governance.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS:

From a realist perspective, techno-polarity reflects a perpetuation of power competition, where states seek dominance through technological superiority in an anarchic international system. This power maximization can be observed in recent instance where The Pentagon invested a hefty amount in AI development for defence superiority [1]. Structural realism, as developed by Kenneth Waltz [2], suggests that states seek to balance power through resources, which ultimately leads to a zero-sum tech competition as seen in the US efforts to curtail Huawei's global reach [3]. Contemporary realists

like Joseph Nye, have highlighted how cyber capabilities have become tools for coercion and competition, paralleling the way nuclear weapons reshaped geopolitics in the 20th century. The Russian cyberattacks on the US (2016) illustrate techno-polar competition in the digital domain [4].

From the lens of liberals, technology is a tool that can enhance global collaboration, create mutual benefits, and reduce conflict through interdependence. Robert Keohane's concept of complex interdependence argues that technological interconnectedness in global digital economy that bind states together making cooperation more beneficial than confrontation [5]. This has given rise to a new, unexplored realm of tech-centric treaties, groupings and initiatives like United Nation's Internet Governance Forum in 2006, Global Partnership on AI in 2020, QUAD's Tech collaboration of 2021, and WEF's Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution among others. John Ikenberry's contemporary work on liberal internationalism highlights how technology can promote democratic values and liberal norms across the world. The spread of the internet and social media is seen to support democratic movements and open societies. The spread of Arab Spring presented a concrete case of how Facebook, Twitter and other social media can be employed to transcend movements beyond borders [6].

Constructivists, with their principal idea of technology is not neutral, brings a distinctive perspective which incorporates unique relationship between societal agents like values, beliefs, norms, background of the developer and technology. Scholars like Amitav Acharya explored the idea of Technological Nationalism and illustrated how national identity and historical experiences shape a country's approach towards technological development [7]. Aadhar, the world's largest biometric ID system, exemplifies the above argument. It was India's successful attempt to construct a unique digital infrastructure that supports inclusive governance. It highlights how technology is intertwined with national identity and governance norms in India and later during in post covid phase, India highlighted achievement of digital vaccination certificate in various international forums which perfectly aligns with Kanti Bajpai's study on India's Strategic Culture mentions how India's historical happenings, particularly the Non-Aligned stance during the Cold War, guides India's digital diplomacy. Conversely, Technological Determinism asserts that inherent properties of a technology, such as the internet, shape human behaviour and social interactions in a deterministic manner [8].

Post-colonial outlook towards techno-polarity argues how technological dominance perpetuates historical patterns of inequality and exploitation. Continuing Global North-South Divide as visualised by the Brandt Line, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak argues, Global South remains dependent on the technological advancements of the Global North and is seen as consumers rather than producers of technology [9]. However, with coming up of tech powers, such as India (Software and IT services), Brazil (Agri-tech), Vietnam (Manufacturing and Electronics) contemporary relevance of this concept is contestable. Another aspect of post-colonial perspective is digital colonialism through cultural colonialism, often talked by scholars like David Harvey [10] which can explain events like Facebook's data collection practices including harvesting data from users in developing countries with limited privacy protections [11] or Netflix's global content strategy to prioritize Western series and films, overshadowing local content and cultural expressions in former colonies [12].

MAJOR PLAYERS IN THE TECHNO-GEOPOLITICS

The USA's early investments in sectors like space and the internet and establishment of institutions like Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency laid the groundwork for its leadership in the emerging techno-polar world order. Springing tech giants like Apple, Microsoft, Google contributing to the rise of Silicon Valley placed the US at the core of global tech innovation sphere which nurtured a robust venture capital ecosystem fuelled by innovation and risk-taking. With institutions like MIT, US has been at the forefront of AI research and development. It took lead in setting global technological standards by steering organizations such as the ITU (International Telecommunication Union) and the ISO (International Organization for Standardization). Post this, USA indulged in heavy tech diplomacy building strategic alliances with other tech leading blocs and nations, maintaining control over critical digital infrastructure, such as undersea cables and cloud servers, which has given it significant strategic advantages.

China's rise is not just a result of its economic ambitions but also of its carefully designed strategic vision to influence global standards. Made in China 2025 initiative, launched in 2015, proved to be remarkable for the country and has helped evolving as a leader in high-tech industries like semiconductors, AI, and robotics. Digital Silk Road initiative, a crucial component of the Belt and Road initiative, directed at expansion of China's technological influence by

boosting exports of digital infrastructure such as 5G networks and satellite systems to developing countries, has strengthened China's soft power in this techno-polar age [13]. Under the guise of digital infrastructure, surveillance technologies being exported has raised concerns about the spread of digital authoritarianism. However, apart from international resistance, China is facing internal challenges in sustaining its technological growth, mainly due to its dependency on foreign technology for critical component. On a heavier note, China is will attempting to reset the global power dynamics through its pursuit of technological rise.

The European Union is strategically repositioning itself as well to assert its digital sovereignty in the newfangled tech-driven world order. Concerns over data privacy, cybersecurity, and the influence of foreign technology giants on European markets is defining EU's approach. By enforcing rigorous data protection standards, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has established the EU as a global leader in data privacy having a significant impact beyond European borders, influencing data protection laws worldwide, including adaptations like Japan's Act on the Protection of Personal Information and California's Consumer Privacy Act [14]. On similar lines, recent acts like The Digital Markets Act (DMA) and Digital Services Act (DSA), introduced in 2022, are significant in curbing the power of tech giants with effective set of regulations, establishing a fair playing field for digital markets and ensuring a safer digital environment [15]. As the techno-polar world order evolves, the EU's commitment to tech regulation and digital sovereignty will be vital in shaping a balanced and secure global digital ambience. However, this will also be a test of EU's endeavours to maintain a cohesion among the member states and address any sort of digital divide between them.

Surfacing new players in advanced techs are trying to alter the techno-geopolitics as well. South Korea, home to tech giants like Samsung and LG, is racing against leading competitors, especially in Asia, like Japan and India, through its advancements in electronics and telecommunications [16]. Israel, being tagged as "a start-up nation" has a sharp strategic focus on development of advanced cyber defence systems, positioned it as a defining player in global security technologies arena [17]. Companies like Vingroup in Vietnam are leading the advancements in manufacturing, especially in technical textiles and semiconductors, which is repositioning Vietnam in Southeast Asia as a tech hub

leading to the route of an influencer in global tech landscape [18].

India's placement in Techno-polar world order

With first modern computer modern computer installed at the Indian Statistical Institute in Kolkata in the 1950s, India witnessed a beginning of what was to be one of the future pillars of diplomacy. Constitution of Bhabha Committee and establishment of Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) in late 1960s marked the onset of IT industry in India. Since then, rapid advancements across numerous fronts including AI, Big Data, space exploration, fintech, and defence tech are significantly shaping its diplomatic and foreign policy landscape [19]. In AI, India progressed multidimensionally targeting multiple areas like health, education, city planning, banking among others which earned India 6th position on Stanford's Global AI Vibrancy ranking. AI becoming a tool for Indian diplomacy which is evident from events like India joining Global Partnership on AI, US-India Artificial Intelligence (USIAI) initiative and recent partnership with Germany to set up AI initiatives focusing on healthcare and sustainability [20]. Rollout of 5G trials in India has attracted partnerships with global tech giants such as Qualcomm and Intel. Like China, India is attempting to export 5G tech and has a significant share in that amounting to Rs 25200 crores worth of telecom equipment and accessories last year. Participation in international events like Mobile World Congress and collaboration with leading players as brightened the prospects for India's tech diplomacy. With successful missions like Mangalyan and Chandrayan 3, India has demonstrated sheer will and capabilities towards space exploration, which has elevated its status in global space community, leading to opening of all new space-diplomacy domain. India not just collaborated with countries like US, Russia, and France, but has also emerged as leader in regional space cooperation, with initiatives like South Asia Satellite (GSAT-9) and the BIMSTEC satellite [21]. India's successful Anti Satellite (ASAT) missile test demonstrated its capabilities in space defence and strategic deterrence thereby securing a recognition and ability to influence global space governance, as demonstrated through its active involvement in United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS) [22]. This helped India to establish diplomatic ties with nations such as the US on a front which has been historically imperative. Recent Indo-Israel Agricultural Project on innovative irrigation and

farming techniques exemplifies the kind of statecraft frontier agri-technologies have opened for India [23].

Flagship initiatives like Make in India, by Indian government, aimed at making India a manufacturing hub, later recognized as one of a global best practice, attracted tech tycoons like Apple and Samsung to not just invest hefty amount but establish and expand their stores in India, which amplifies India's tech image globally. The success of the automotive industry under Make in India is exemplified by companies like Hyundai and Suzuki expanding their manufacturing bases in India, not just to cater to the domestic market but also to export vehicles to Europe and Africa. India Initiatives like Aadhar and Unified Payments Interface under Digital India programme has been cited as a model for not just other emerging economies but also some for some developed ones. These efforts accelerated India's digital growth while escalating its international competitiveness.

Cyber diplomacy and Global Governance in digital age

As the internet transcends borders, cyber diplomacy is capturing the core of defence and foreign policies. Cyber Diplomacy Toolbox, an initiative of EU launched in 2017 with target of providing the EU with a set of diplomatic measure to deter malicious cyber exploits. In July 2020, the EU imposed its first-ever cyber sanctions on Russian, Chinese, and North Korean entities linked to high-profile cyberattacks, including the 2017 WannaCry ransomware attack. The initiative exemplifies how regional organizations can leverage diplomatic tools to enhance cybersecurity and influence global cyber norms. It also demonstrates the strategic use of restrictive measures like sanctions to deter state-sponsored cyberattacks, highlighting the role of diplomacy in managing conflicts in the digital domain [24].

In 21st century, the rise of big tech corporations has dramatically reshaped not only the global economy but also the landscape of international policy. Having shaken the world after Facebook's interference in the 2016 United States presidential election and Britain's Referendum, social media platforms' involvement in international politics has remained a global issue. The News Media Bargaining Code was passed by the Australian government in 2020, to urge Google and Facebook to compensate the publishers of Australian news content. It was the reaction to the increased

dominance of tech giants. Google vehemently rejected the bill and threatened that it might be forced to deactivate the search engine in the country. The increasing pressure from Google's lobbying finally yielded results when the Australian government made some significant concessions in the final copy of the bill which favoured Google immensely. This episode shows how powerful tech giants can bend the law and shaping it in their favour whenever national governments try to regulate them. It underscores the importance of international cooperation and strong regulatory frameworks to ensure that these companies do not undermine the sovereignty of national governments [25].

Challenges and Opportunities of Techno-polarity

Ethical concerns, particularly in AI ethics, data collection and surveillance, concerns are striking in terms of tech governance and regulation. In 2018, AI tools designed by Amazon to assist in the recruitment process, proved to be prejudiced against female candidates as the training dataset consisted of mostly male profiles. This is one of many example that showcases the necessity of intensified control and reasonable AI [26]. Similarly, the influence of Facebook, in Myanmar's Rohingya crisis fuelled ethnic violence demonstrate misuse of data by the data collectors and implies towards the urgency legislating a global data privacy norm. The balance between security and individual rights is a critical issue in modern governance. China's social credit system, which includes facial recognition as one of its aspects, is a typical example of ethical aspects of surveillance. The system observes the behaviour of citizens and assigns them scores regarding the rights of utilizing services and services, thus threatening privacy and state control [27].

The shifting towards techno-polar world has enlarged the Digital Divide both between societies as well as within societies. This digital divide amplifies technological, infrastructural, and digital literacy inequalities that may slow down global growth and promote inequity across social structures. This results in people in the developing nations having less access to sophisticated technologies than their counterparts in the developed nations. As per International Telecommunication Union, availability of internet connection remains low in Sub-Saharan Africa with a connectivity rate of 30% as compared to nearly 80% in Europe, thus restricting its role in the global digital economy. Efforts to bridge this divide have begun. Initiatives like United Nations' 2030 Agenda that brings focus on the digital divide as one of the key development goals in the SDGs can assist in reversing this split.

CONCLUSION

In this ongoing and unending play of a techno-polar world, authority at the global level will tend to be a derivative of the ability of actors to create, transform and control the technological sphere. Artillery of the future conflicts will be the cloud and the code rather than the terrain. Upcoming chapters of international relations and power balances being scripted in the language of technology which has never been so important before. Possessing a pool of talented IT professionals, a growing IT community, and a vision of country's digitization, can ascend India up as an imposing tech giant. However, this is a future filled with challenges in getting to that point when technology has become the weapon, will involve a careful balancing act of building strategic partnerships while ensuring that the country maintains its strategic sovereignty. Steering through such complexities successfully, will be rewarded in the form of an opportunity to redraw the map of world power in this new historic age.

The techno-polar world order that has emerged and is still unfolding, thus offering a lot of scope for investigation. Further research must focus on the complex interaction of technology and world politics: pinpointing how the technologies such as quantum computing, artificial intelligence, biotechnology will alter the world's politics. Academics should pay more attention to the dynamics of platform actors and states, as well as the moral and regulatory issues associated with technology progress. The awareness of the socio-political effects of technology based on the techno-geopolitics, techno-capitalism and digital divide that this paper presents will be of use in identifying how nations can apply technological power appropriately. The investigation of these future research directions is not just an intellectual exercise but a mission on how our new civilization defines the solutions to the challenges presented by the all-new techno-age.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable

Authors' contributions

RKP, SB & SS was responsible for the first manuscript draft. All authors contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

Funding

No funding received for this study.

Availability of data and materials

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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